

Polygonal Endplate Connections in Circular Hollow Section Members Verification and Design Proposal using Discontinuity Layout Optimization

Ralph Timmers^{*,a}, Robert Lang^a

^aUniversity of Innsbruck, Department of Structural Engineering and Material Sciences,
Unit for Steel Construction and Mixed Building Technology, Austria
ralph.timmers@uibk.ac.at, robert.lang@uibk.ac.at

ABSTRACT

Joining circular hollow section members with bolted circular endplates is a typical design method. Using polygonal endplates can be a cheap and easy-to-manufacture alternative. The plate deforms under a tension force, resulting in prying forces, which influence the resistance of the connection. The so-called T-stub model from the EN 1993-1-8 can consider this complex behaviour. Nevertheless, the connections mentioned above are not part of the EN 1993-1-8, and no research was found in the literature on such connections.

The present research deals with this construction method by analysing connections with polygonal endplates and six bolts. The Discontinuity Layout Optimization (DLO) method is used, where a linear programming algorithm searches for the kinematic yield line mechanism that results in the lowest resistance of the connection. The kinematic failure mechanisms from the DLO simulations can be visualised, gaining a deeper insight and understanding of the failure behaviour compared to other methods, like the typically used FEM. First, the DLO concept is introduced, including verification by recalculating experimental tests on similar connections. Afterwards, a parameter study is worked out using different plate thicknesses and geometrical dimensions. The evolution of the different yield line mechanisms is systematically analysed and serves as the basis for a design model, which is Eurocode conform and could easily be implemented in the EN 1993-1-8.

Keywords: Limit state analysis, Discontinuity Layout Optimization, Yield-line mechanism, T-stub model

1 INTRODUCTION

Joining circular hollow section members with bolted circular endplates is a typical design method. Using polygonal endplates instead, as shown in *Fig. 1*, can be a cheap and easy-to-manufacture alternative. The endplate deforms under a tension force, resulting in prying forces, which influence the resistance of the connection. This complex behaviour can be considered with the so-called T-stub model, which is also part of EN 1993-1-8 (1). However, these connections are not part of EN 1993-1-8 due to the lack of effective lengths (yield lines). No research on such connections was found in the literature, which means that systematic investigations into the evolution of the different local and global failure mechanisms are needed. The evolution of the failure mechanisms can also serve as a basis for developing a design proposal.

The present research addresses this need for more knowledge by analysing such connections with six bolts using the Discontinuity Layout Optimization (DLO) method. Within this method, a linear programming algorithm searches for the kinematic yield line mechanism (YLM) that results in the lowest resistance of the connection. The failure mechanisms can be displayed and compared. The DLO method provides a deeper insight and understanding of the kinematic failure mechanisms compared to other methods, such as the commonly used FEM.

Fig. 1. Polygonal endplate connection with six bolts, taken and modified from (2)

The DLO method was first investigated to analyse plane plasticity and geotechnical problems and was later extended to 3D problems, see e.g. (3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8). Further research led to a modified DLO formulation for structures mainly loaded in bending, like reinforced concrete slabs, see e.g. (9, 10, 11). The application area has also been extended to analyse typical problems in steel structures. First, the bearing capacity of bolted connections with a single bolt was investigated (12). Later, the method was used to analyse bolted connections where the plate is in bending. The bolts and the resulting prying forces are included in the numerical model (13, 14, 15, 16). Therefore, the DLO method can be used as a generalised method to analyse arbitrary T-stub connections.

The structure of the present research is as follows: Section 2 introduces the DLO concept, including verification by recalculating experimental tests on similar connections. Afterwards, a parameter study is worked out in Section 3. The case with six bolts from Fig. 1 was used as a reference. Different plate thicknesses and geometrical dimensions are used as parameters. The evolution of the different yield line mechanisms is systematically analysed by increasing the plate thickness from very thin to thick. In Section 4, a Eurocode-compliant design proposal is developed. The numerical results are the basis for the design proposal, which could easily be implemented in the EN 1993-1-8. Finally, a summary and outlook are given in Section 5.

2 DISCONTINUITY LAYOUT OPTIMIZATION

The DLO method is based on the upper bound theorem. The geometry of the endplate and the bolts must first be discretised by a large number of possible yield lines. After defining the external loads, a linear programming algorithm searches for the kinematic failure mechanism, that gives the lowest resistance to the problem. To do this, the internal work $\mathbf{g}^T \mathbf{p}$ from the bolts and yield lines and the external work $\mathbf{f}_L^T \mathbf{d}$ from the loads were equated, where λ serves as load multiplier. Additionally, linear equalities and inequalities are required to guarantee real kinematic mechanisms. The formulation of the DLO method used here is given by Eq. (1).

$$\min_{\mathbf{d}, \mathbf{p}} \lambda \cdot \mathbf{f}_L^T \mathbf{d} = \mathbf{g}^T \mathbf{p} \quad \text{such that} \quad \begin{cases} \mathbf{Bd} = \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{Np} - \mathbf{d} = \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{f}_L^T \mathbf{d} = 1 \\ \mathbf{p} \geq \mathbf{0} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

More detailed information on the DLO method, and especially the formulation used here, can be found in the previously mentioned literature in Section 1. The software MATLAB (17) was used to

solve the linear programming problem from *Eq. (1)*. The DLO method is used for scientific purposes only.

The DLO method has been verified among others in (14) by recalculating a large number of experiments from the literature. In addition, further verification on circular hollow section members is now considered. Experimental results on polygonal endplates are not available at the moment; therefore, similar experiments on circular endplates were used (own experiments on polygonal endplates are planned for the future). An experimental study on 63 circular hollow section members with circular endplates with six bolts was published in (18). Some of the connections failed due to weld or tube failure. These tests were not included in the verification as these failure mechanisms are not part of the current research and the numerical model. The resulting 40 tests were recalculated using the DLO method.

Experimental and theoretical investigations into the T-stub behaviour of bolted connections were carried out by Zoetemeijer in 1974 (19). Zoetemeijer proposed that the bolt resistance should be based on the yield strength, including a sufficient margin against bolt rupture, which he assumed with 70 % of the ultimate load. This bolt resistance is similar to the resistance from EN 1993-1-5, given in *Eq. (2)*, when the yield strength is used instead of the tensile strength with $\gamma_{M2} = 1.25$.

$$F_{t,Bolt} = 0.9 \frac{f_{ub}}{\gamma_{M2}} A_s = 0.72 f_{ub} A_s \cong 0.9 f_{yb} A_s \quad (2)$$

Own recalculations with the DLO method also showed a satisfactory agreement with the test results (15). The value of 0.9 can also be seen as a simplified reduction factor, which considers the bending stresses in the bolt due to deformations of the endplate, which is explained in more detail in (20, 21).

The recalculations with DLO were performed with the measured yield strength f_y of the plates and bolt resistance according to *Eq. (2)* to consider the bending of the bolts. For comparison, the tests were also recalculated with a modified yield strength according to *Eq. (3)* to account for the non-linear behaviour of the endplate. This assumption can be found in various publications, e.g. (22).

$$f_{y,mod} = \frac{f_y + 2f_u}{3} \quad (3)$$

Fig. 2a shows a comparison of the experimentally and numerically obtained ultimate loads. All resistances are normalised to the maximum resistance of the connection, which results in $F_{max} = \sum F_{Bolt}$, where F_{Bolt} is the real bolt resistance. It can be seen that all tests (except one) are on the safe side when using the yield strength f_y for the endplates. Not enough details are given in (18) to verify this single test result. The DLO method has also been verified by other test results (14, 15); therefore, the single unsafe test result has been neglected. *Fig. 2b* shows the normalised resistances compared to their β -values from *Eq. (4)*.

$$\beta = \frac{F_{max} - F_{DLO}}{F_{DLO}} \quad (4)$$

The results are more conservative for increasing β -values (thinner endplates), as shown in *Fig. 2b*. This can be explained as follows. Thinner endplates tend to have large deformations. Due to the membrane effect, these connections achieve higher resistances than the numerical simulations, where the membrane effect is not included.

Fig. 2c-d shows the resistances when using the modified yield strength $f_{y,mod}$ according to *Eq. (3)* for the endplates. The numerically obtained resistances are higher compared to *Fig. 2a-b*, but the basic behaviour of the joints remains the same.

Fig. 2. Comparison of the experimentally and numerically obtained ultimate loads: a-b) Yield strength f_y of the plate; c-d) modified yield strength $f_{y,mod}$ in the plate

3 PARAMETRIC STUDY AND FAILURE MECHANISMS

A parameter study was carried out to gain a deeper understanding of the failure mechanisms. The geometry of the endplate connection with six bolts shown in Fig. 1 is defined by the distances m and e , which can be expressed by the radii R_1 , R_2 and R_3 . In all cases, six bolts M16 8.8 were used (bolthole diameter $d_0 = 18\text{mm}$), each with a resistance of $F_{t,Rd} = 90,43\text{kN}$, according to EN 1993-1-8 (1). The parameter study was carried out for different constellations, with a constant value of $m = 40\text{mm}$. The ratio e/m was varied by 0.5, 1, 1.5 and 2, and R_1/m varied by 1, 2 and 4. The plate thickness t_{pl} was slowly increased for each constellation, from a very thin plate of 2mm thickness up to a thick plate of 30mm thickness. In this way, all the typical failure mechanisms can be obtained, i.e. pure plate failure for thin plates, combined plate and bolt failure for moderately thick plates, and pure bolt failure for thick plates.

The obtained yield line mechanisms (YLMs) are shown in Fig. 3. The YLMs are sorted according to the failure mechanisms corresponding to the plate thickness. A pure plate failure occurs for thin plates, as shown in Fig. 3a-b. For small values of R_1/R_2 , a global failure of the whole plate occurs (Fig. 3a), while for larger values, a local failure around the bolts occurs (Fig. 3b). For moderately thick plates, the failure mechanism results in a combined plate and bolt failure, as shown in Fig. 3c-d. Again, for small values of R_1/R_2 , the failure mechanism shows a global failure (Fig. 3c), while for larger values, a more local failure occurs around the bolt holes (Fig. 3d). For thick plates, a pure bolt failure was found, i.e. the plate does not deform, and no prying forces occur (Fig. 3e). The resistance of this failure mechanism is always an upper limit and can be calculated as the sum of the six bolt resistances $F_{max,Rd} = \sum F_{t,Rd}$.

a) Global failure of the plate

b) Local failure of the plate

c) Global plate and bolt failure

d) Local plate and bolt failure

e) Pure bolt failure

Fig. 3. Yield line mechanisms from DLO (red and blue: positive and negative rotations; green: translation of the bolts), taken and modified from (2)

For comparison, all systems were also calculated with a circular endplate of radius R_3 (compare Fig. 1). The resistances with polygonal endplates are equal to or slightly lower than those with circular endplates. It is obvious that the resistances are the same for pure bolt failure. On average, the resistances of circular endplates are 7 % higher when all the calculated examples are taken into account, but in single cases, the resistances were also found to be 30 % higher.

Fig. 4. Assumed yield line mechanisms for the design proposal (red and blue: positive and negative rotations; green: translation of the bolts), taken and modified from (2)

4 DESIGN PROPOSAL

For practical purposes, a design proposal was developed based on the obtained YLMs from Fig. 3. To be Eurocode conform, the design proposal was developed for the different failure modes from the code, i.e., pure plate failure (Mode 1), combined plate and bolt failure (Mode 2), and pure bolt failure (Mode 3). The assumed YLMs are shown in Fig. 4. The plastic resistance of a single yield line with a rectangular cross-section per length is given by Eq. (5).

$$m_{pl,Rd} = \frac{t_{pl}^2 f_y}{4\gamma_{M0}} \quad (5)$$

4.1 Mode 1 failure

For Mode 1 failure, a global and a local YLM was taken into account. The resistance of the global YLM is obtained from the work equation, which can be formulated from *Fig. 4a*. It was considered that $\alpha = u/m$ and the sum of infinite dihedral angles α' gives $2\pi\alpha$. The work equation and the resulting resistance are given by *Eq. (6)*.

$$\begin{aligned}
 F_{1,glo}u &= m_{pl,Rd}l_{1a,glo}\alpha + m_{pl,Rd}l_{1b,glo}\alpha + m_{pl,Rd}l_{1,\alpha}2\pi\alpha \\
 l_{1a,glo} &= 2\pi R_1 \\
 l_{1b,glo} &= 2\pi\left(R_1 + m - \frac{d_0}{2}\right) \\
 l_{1,\alpha} &= m - \frac{d_0}{2} \\
 F_{1,glo} &= \frac{m_{pl,Rd}(l_{1a,glo} + l_{1b,glo} + 2\pi l_{1,\alpha})}{m}
 \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

The work equation and resistance for the local failure mechanism can be obtained from *Fig. 4b*, resulting in *Eq. (7)*. The angle φ results in $2\pi/3$. Furthermore, an upper limit has been defined for the local yield line $l_{1a,loc}$ to exclude that the yield line overlaps with the yield lines in the adjacent corners.

$$\begin{aligned}
 F_{1,loc}u &= 6m_{pl,Rd}l_{1a,loc}\alpha + 6m_{pl,Rd}l_{1b,loc}\alpha \\
 l_{1a,loc} &= \frac{2\pi}{3}(m + e) \leq \frac{2\pi}{3}\left(\frac{R_1 + m + e}{2}\right) \\
 l_{1b,loc} &= \frac{2\pi}{3}\left(e + \frac{d_0}{2}\right) \\
 F_{1,loc} &= \frac{6m_{pl,Rd}(l_{1a,loc} + l_{1b,loc})}{m}
 \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

4.2 Mode 2 failure

A global and a local YLM was also considered for Mode 2 failure. The work equation and resistance of the global YLM can be formulated from *Fig. 4c*. Compared to Mode 1 failure, $\alpha = u/(m + e) = u'/e$ was taken into account. It was also taken into account that the YLM can form either with $l_{2a,\alpha}$ or with $l_{2b,\alpha}$, depending on the actual length. The dihedral angle for the polygonal endplate with six bolts is $\alpha' = \alpha$.

$$\begin{aligned}
 F_{2,glo}u &= m_{pl,Rd}l_{2,glo}\alpha + 6m_{pl,Rd}l_{2,\alpha}\alpha' + 6F_{t,Rd}u' \\
 l_{2,glo} &= 2\pi R_1 \\
 l_{2a,\alpha} &= m + e - d_0 \\
 l_{2b,\alpha} &= \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}(R_1 + m + e) - R_1 \\
 l_{2,\alpha} &= \min(l_{2a,\alpha}, l_{2b,\alpha}) \\
 F_{2,glo} &= \frac{m_{pl,Rd}l_{2,glo} + 6(m_{pl,Rd}l_{2,\alpha} + eF_{t,Rd})}{m + e}
 \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

The local failure mechanism from *Fig. 4d* results in *Eq. (9)*. Again, an upper limit on the length of the yield line has been chosen to avoid overlapping, similar to *Eq. (7)*.

$$F_{2,loc}u = 6m_{pl,Rd}l_{2,loc}\alpha + 6F_{t,Rd}u'$$

$$l_{2,loc} = \frac{2\pi}{3}(m+e) \leq \frac{2\pi}{3}\left(\frac{R_1+m+e}{2}\right)$$

$$F_{2,loc} = \frac{6(m_{pl,Rd}l_{2,loc} + eF_{t,Rd})}{m+e}$$
(9)

4.3 Mode 3 failure

As mentioned above, Mode 3 failure is always an upper limit and corresponds to pure bolt failure (see *Fig. 3e*). The resistance of this failure mode can simply be calculated as the sum of the individual bolt resistances, resulting in *Eq. (10)*.

$$F_3 = 6F_{t,Rd}$$
(10)

4.4 Resistance of the connection

The resistances defined above have been developed based on the upper bound theorem. Therefore, the final resistance of the connection can be written as the minimum of the different YLMs, as given in *Eq. (11)*.

$$F_{T,Rd} = \min(F_{1,glo}, F_{1,loc}, F_{2,glo}, F_{2,loc}, F_3)$$
(11)

Fig. 5 compares the numerically obtained resistances from DLO and the design proposal according to *Eq. (11)*. The different failure modes are marked graphically. The deviations to the unsafe side are less than 10 %.

Fig. 5. Comparison of numerically obtained resistances with design proposal

It was shown in Section 3 that the resistances for circular endplates are, in all cases, higher than those for polygonal endplates, which means that the design proposal can also be used for circular endplates with six bolts.

5 SUMMARY AND OUTLOOK

First, the DLO concept was introduced, including verification on similar connections. This numerical model was used for a parametric study on polygonal endplates with six bolts. The plate

thickness was increased for each geometry to obtain all the different YLMs. The YLMs were systematically classified into pure plate failure, combined plate and bolt failure, and pure bolt failure. Within this research, new failure mechanisms were discovered. Based on these YLMs, a Eurocode-compliant design proposal was developed. The design proposal was shown to be in good agreement with the numerically obtained resistances, with deviations to the unsafe side of less than 10 %.

Fig. 6. Polygonal endplate connections with 4, 6, 8 and 12 bolts, taken from (2).

Since the abstract was submitted for this conference, a more extensive parameter study on circular hollow section members with polygonal endplate connections has been carried out. Different numbers of bolts have been investigated. It was found that the presented design proposal, with some modifications, is also valid for polygonal endplate connections with 4, 6, 8 and 12 bolts, as shown in Fig. 6. Details are given in (2). Furthermore, investigations on rectangular hollow section members and rectangular endplates, with and without chamfers, have also been presented in (13), including a design proposal. Experimental studies are planned for the future to verify the numerically discovered YLMs.

REFERENCES

1. **EN 1993-1-8.** Eurocode 3: Design of Steel Structures, Part 1-8: Design of Joints. CEN European Committee for Standardization. Brussels, Belgium. 2012.
2. **Timmers, R. and Lang, R.** Bemessungsvorschlag für geschraubte, polygonale Endplatten bei runden Hohlprofilen unter Zug. *Stahlbau*. 92, 2023, Vol. 12, pp. 777-787. DOI: 10.1002/stab.202300039.
3. **Smith, C. and Gilbert, M.** Application of discontinuity layout optimization to plane plasticity problems. *Proceedings of the Royal Society A* 463. Vol. 2086, pp. 2461-2484. DOI: 10.1098/rspa.2006.1788.
4. —. Identification of rotational failure mechanisms in cohesive media using discontinuity layout optimisation. *Géotechnique*. 63, 2013, Vol. 14, pp. 1194-1208. DOI: 10.1680/geot.12.P.082.
5. **Bauer, S. and Lackner, R.** Gradient-based adaptive discontinuity layout optimization for the prediction of strength properties in matrix-inclusion materials. *International Journal of Solids and Structures*. 63, 2015, pp. 82-98. DOI: j.ijsolstr.2015.02.042.
6. **Zhang, Y., Zhuang, X. and Lackner, R.** Stability analysis of shotcrete supported crown of NATM tunnels with discontinuity layout optimization. *International journal for numerical and analytical methods in geomechanics*. 42, 2018, Vol. 11, pp. 1199-1216. DOI: 10.1002/nag.2775.
7. **Hawksbee, S., Smith, C. and Gilbert, M.** Application of discontinuity layout optimization to three-dimensional plasticity problems. *Proceedings of the Royal Society A* 469. 2155, 2013, Vol. 20130009, DOI: 10.1098/rspa.2013.0009.

8. **Zhang, Y.** Multi-slicing strategy for the three-dimensional discontinuity layout optimization (3D DLO). *International journal for numerical and analytical methods in geomechanics*. 41, 2017, Vol. 4, pp. 488-507. DOI: 10.1002/nag.2566.
9. **Gilbert, M., He, L. and Pritchard, T. J.** The yield-line method for concrete slabs: automated at last. *The Structural Engineer*. 93, 2015, Vol. 10, pp. 44-48.
10. **Gilbert, M., et al.** Automatic yield-line analysis of slabs using discontinuity layout optimization. *Proceedings of the Royal Society A. Mathematical, physical, and engineering sciences*. 470, 2014, Vol. 2168. 20140071, DOI: 10.1098/rspa.2014.0071.
11. **He, L., Gilbert, M. and Shepherd, M.** Automatic Yield-Line Analysis of Practical Slab Configurations via Discontinuity Layout Optimization. *Journal of Structural Engineering*. 143, 2017, Vol. 7. 4017036, DOI: 10.1061/(ASCE)ST.1943-541X.0001700.
12. **Timmers, R.** Application of Discontinuity Layout Optimization to Steel Parts and Steel Connections with a Single Bolt. *Applied Sciences*. 10, 2020, Vol. 11, 3783. DOI: 2076-3417/10/11/3783.
13. **Timmers, R. and Lang, R.** Yield-line mechanisms and design proposal for endplate connections in rectangular hollow section members in tension. *Engineering Structures*. 2023, Vol. 279, 115560. DOI: 10.1016/j.engstruct.2022.115560.
14. —. Zur Traglastberechnung geschraubter Kopfplattenverbindungen bei Hohlprofilen mittels DLO. *Stahlbau*. 2021, Vol. 91, 3, DOI: 10.1002/stab.202100079.
15. **Timmers, R.** Generalized method for identifying yield-line patterns in T-stubs using discontinuity layout optimization. *Engineering Structures*. 244, 2021, 112802. DOI: 10.1016/j.engstruct.2021.112802.
16. **Timmers, R. and Lang, R.** Yield-line Mechanisms of Endplate Connections with Eight Bolts and Circular Bolt Configurations using DLO. *ce/papers*. 5, 2022, Vol. 4, pp. 194-203. SDSS 2022, Aveiro, Portugal. DOI: 10.1002/cepa.1745.
17. **The Math Works.** Matlab R2020a (Software). <https://de.mathworks.com> (accessed on 29.11.2023).
18. **Kato, B. and Hirose, R.** Bolted Tension Flanges Joining Circular Hollow Section Members. *Journal of Constructional Steel Research*. 1985, Vol. 5.
19. **Zoetemeijer, P.** A design method for the tension side of statically loaded, bolted beam-to-column connections. *Heron*. 1, 1974, Vol. 20, pp. 1-59.
20. **Couchaux, M., Ryan, I. and Hjiij, M.** Plastic resistance of L-stubs joints subjected to tensile forces. *Conference Proceedings SDSS 2010 Stability and Ductility of Steel Structures, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil*. 2010.
21. **Couchaux, M., et al.** Tensile resistance of L-stubs. *Journal of Constructional Steel Research*. 138, 2017, pp. 131-149. DOI: 10.1016/j.jcsr.2017.06.016.
22. **Packer, J.A., Bruno, L. and Birkemoe, P.C.** Limit Analysis of Bolted RHS Flange Plate Joints. *Journal of Structural Engineering*. 115, 1989, Vol. 9, pp. 2226-2242.